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CEO Chair Separation And Deposit Mobilization Of Commercial Banks In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of CEO-Chairman separation on the deposit mobilization ratio and performing loan ratio of commercial banks in Nigeria. Two research objectives, questions, and hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. An ex-post facto research design was adopted, utilizing secondary data sourced from the financial reports of Nigerian commercial banks. The population consisted of all 24 commercial banks licensed by the Central Bank of Nigeria, with a census survey technique employed. Data analysis was conducted using descriptive statistics and Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression techniques. The results revealed that CEO-Chairman separation has a weak but positive and significant effect on both deposit mobilization and performing loan ratios. This indicates that governance reforms aimed at separating the CEO and Chairman roles can enhance deposit mobilization and improve asset quality in commercial banks. It was concluded that CEO-Chairman separation improves corporate governance, which, in turn, strengthens the financial performance of Nigerian banks. It was recommended that regulatory bodies enforce stricter adoption of this policy to enhance the stability and efficiency of the banking sector.

Keywords: CEO-Chairman Separation, Deposit Mobilization, Performing Loan Ratio, Commercial Banks, Corporate Governance

INTRODUCTION

Corporate governance has become a focal point in the financial sector due to its influence on bank performance, especially in emerging markets like Nigeria. One of the critical aspects of corporate governance is the separation of the roles of the Chief Executive Officer (CEO) and the Chairperson of the Board of Directors. This separation, often referred to as "CEO-chair separation," is designed to create a balance of power and enhance transparency in decision-making. In the context of Nigerian commercial banks, where deposit mobilization plays a pivotal role in overall financial stability, the dynamics of CEO-chair separation and its influence on deposit mobilization are worthy of critical examination (Adeyemi & Akinlo, 2020).

Deposit mobilization is a core function of commercial banks, directly linked to their liquidity, lending capacity, and profitability. It refers to the ability of a bank to attract deposits from the public, which can be influenced by various factors including corporate governance practices, market confidence, and operational efficiency (Bello & Suleiman, 2021). The relationship between CEO-chair separation and deposit mobilization is particularly relevant in Nigeria's banking sector due to the sector's history of corporate governance failures and systemic crises, such as the banking crisis of 2009 (Sanusi, 2010). These crises underscored the need for stronger governance frameworks that enhance transparency and accountability, ensuring that depositors' funds are safeguarded.

The rationale behind separating the roles of CEO and Chair lies in the need to avoid the concentration of power in a single individual, which can lead to conflicts of interest and poor oversight (Klein, 2014). The CEO is responsible for the day-to-day operations of the bank, while the Chairperson provides leadership to the board and ensures that the board functions effectively in its supervisory

role. When these roles are combined, the checks and balances that come from a clear division of responsibilities can be compromised, potentially leading to governance lapses (Fama & Jensen, 1983). This can have direct implications for deposit mobilization, as poor governance can erode public confidence in the bank's management, making it harder to attract deposits.

In Nigeria, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has put in place corporate governance guidelines that encourage the separation of CEO and Chair roles to enhance accountability and governance quality (CBN, 2014). This regulatory push is in line with global best practices, where the separation of powers at the top management level is seen as a means to reduce risks of mismanagement and ensure more robust oversight of banking activities. However, despite these regulations, there are still instances where Nigerian commercial banks have either not adopted this structure or have done so only in form, without significant changes in governance outcomes (Afolabi, 2019).

Research has shown that governance structures, including CEO-chair separation, can significantly affect a bank's ability to mobilize deposits (Okezie & Amos, 2020). Effective governance promotes trust, which is critical in a banking environment where depositors must have confidence in the institution's ability to manage their funds. In situations where there is weak governance, depositors may become hesitant to entrust their money to the bank, leading to lower deposit mobilization. On the other hand, when there is strong governance, with a clear division of responsibilities between the CEO and Chairperson, it can foster an environment of trust and reliability, making it easier for banks to attract deposits (Amidu & Wolfe, 2013).

Moreover, deposit mobilization in Nigeria is influenced by a range of factors beyond corporate governance, including the macroeconomic environment, customer service, and financial product innovation (Ogunleye, 2015). However, corporate governance remains a foundational element that affects the bank's reputation and ability to compete for deposits in a crowded market. The role of governance becomes even more critical in periods of economic downturn or financial instability when depositor confidence can easily be shaken. In such scenarios, banks with robust governance frameworks, including CEO-chair separation, are better positioned to maintain and even grow their deposit base.

Statement of Problem

Corporate governance practices, particularly the separation of the roles of the Chief Executive Officer (CEO) and Chairperson of the Board, have been identified as key determinants of organizational performance and stakeholder confidence in the banking sector (Klein, 2014). In Nigeria, commercial banks rely heavily on deposit mobilization for their liquidity, lending capacity, and overall financial health. However, the effectiveness of these banks in mobilizing deposits is influenced by a range of factors, including their governance structures. Despite regulatory guidelines by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) that encourage the separation of the CEO and Chair roles to improve oversight and accountability (CBN, 2014), there is a lack of empirical evidence on how this governance structure impacts deposit mobilization in Nigerian commercial banks.

Several studies have highlighted the importance of corporate governance in fostering trust and confidence in banks, which is critical for attracting deposits (Okezie & Amos, 2020). However, many Nigerian commercial banks continue to struggle with weak governance structures, which may undermine depositor confidence and affect their ability to mobilize funds (Afolabi, 2019). Additionally, while some banks have implemented the CEO-chair separation in compliance with regulatory requirements, the effectiveness of this separation in driving deposit mobilization remains unclear. The concentration of power in a single individual, often seen in banks where the CEO and Chair roles are combined, can lead to governance failures that negatively impact depositor trust and hinder the bank's ability to attract deposits (Fama & Jensen, 1983).

Given the critical role of deposit mobilization in the sustainability of commercial banks, understanding the relationship between CEO-chair separation and deposit mobilization is essential. This study seeks to address the gap in the literature by investigating how the separation of these leadership roles influences deposit mobilization in Nigerian commercial banks.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study examined CEO-Chairman separation on the asset quality of Commercial banks in Nigeria. Specifically, the study achieved the following:

1. To determine the effect of the CEO-Chairman separation on the deposit mobilization ratio of Commercial banks in Nigeria.
2. To determine the effect of the CEO-Chairman separation on performing loan ratio of Commercial banks in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the effect of the CEO-Chairman separation on the deposit mobilization ratio of Commercial banks in Nigeria?
2. What is the effect of the CEO-Chairman separation on performing loan ratio of Commercial banks in Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and will be tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H0₁: CEO-chairman separation has no significant effect on the deposit mobilization ratio of commercial banks in Nigeria.

H0₂: CEO-Chairman separation has no significant effect on the performing loan ratio of Commercial banks in Nigeria.

Conceptual Review

CEO-Chair Separation refers to the division of roles between the Chief Executive Officer (CEO) and the Chairman of the Board of Directors in a corporate governance framework. In the context of commercial banks, this separation is essential for ensuring checks and balances within the organization. The CEO is responsible for the day-to-day management and operational activities of the bank, while the Chairman oversees the board's strategic direction and supervises the performance of the CEO. Separating these roles prevents excessive concentration of power in one individual, enhancing accountability, transparency, and corporate governance (Fama & Jensen, 1983). In Nigeria, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) mandates this separation to strengthen governance structures in the banking sector (CBN, 2014).

The importance of deposit mobilization in commercial banks cannot be overstated. Deposit mobilization refers to the process by which banks attract and retain customers' deposits, which form a significant portion of their financial base and liquidity. Efficient deposit mobilization is crucial for banks to lend and invest, thus influencing profitability and growth. According to Nwaeze (2020), banks that exhibit sound governance structures, including CEO-Chair separation, are more likely to gain public trust, which positively impacts deposit mobilization. This separation enhances confidence in the bank's leadership and minimizes the risks associated with poor decision-making by preventing the CEO from having unchecked influence over board decisions (Adusei, 2011).

In the Nigerian context, CEO-Chair separation can directly affect deposit mobilization in commercial banks by fostering better governance practices, leading to improved financial stability and increased public confidence. Proper corporate governance, including the separation of leadership roles, reduces the likelihood of mismanagement or fraud, which can have adverse effects on depositors' trust (Olalekan & Adebayo, 2013).

Theoretical Review

1. Agency Theory

Agency theory provides a fundamental basis for understanding the separation of roles between the CEO and the Chairman in corporate governance. This theory posits that conflicts of interest may arise when ownership (shareholders) is separated from control (management), as managers (agents) may not always act in the best interests of the shareholders (principals) (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). By separating the roles of the CEO and the Chairman, banks can minimize the potential for managerial self-interest, as the Chairman can oversee and monitor the actions of the CEO. This structure enhances transparency and accountability, which are crucial for building trust among depositors.

In the context of deposit mobilization in Nigerian banks, CEO-Chair separation aligns with agency theory by ensuring that decision-making processes are more transparent, reducing the likelihood of opportunistic behavior by management. When depositors perceive that a bank has robust governance structures, including independent oversight by a non-executive Chairman, their confidence in the

institution increases, making them more likely to deposit their funds (Olalekan & Adebayo, 2013). This confidence is a key driver in the effective mobilization of deposits, as trust is critical in the banking industry.

2. Stewardship Theory

Stewardship theory, in contrast to agency theory, assumes that managers are stewards of the company and are inherently motivated to act in the best interests of the shareholders (Donaldson & Davis, 1991). According to this theory, there may not always be a need for a rigid separation between the CEO and the Chairman, as executives are viewed as trustworthy and committed to the success of the organization. However, in the banking sector, especially in a developing economy like Nigeria, the stewardship theory is often complemented by the CEO-Chair separation to enhance governance and regulatory compliance.

In the Nigerian banking context, where regulatory frameworks require strict governance standards, combining stewardship with role separation helps balance managerial discretion with oversight. When banks separate the CEO and Chair roles, they create an environment where the CEO can focus on operational efficiency, including strategies for deposit mobilization, while the Chairman ensures that corporate objectives align with the long-term interests of both shareholders and depositors (Nwaeze, 2020). This dual governance structure supports sustainable deposit mobilization by fostering an environment of financial stability and integrity.

Empirical Review

Asogwa (2019) examined the effect of corporate governance leadership models and attributes on firms' earnings quality using evidence from Nigerian quoted firms. This study used an ex-post facto design with two-stage multiple random and fixed effect regression analyses. A sample of 37 quoted firms in the Nigerian Stock Exchange between 2014 and 2018 was selected. The findings indicated that dual board leadership models, where the roles of the CEO and Chairman were separated, significantly improved earnings persistence and value relevance compared to unitary leadership. The study also revealed that the presence of financial expertise among both the CEO and Chair led to higher earnings quality. The findings suggest that dual leadership structures in governance could enhance depositor confidence, which could positively influence deposit mobilization in commercial banks.

Olalekan and Adebayo (2013) explored the relationship between corporate governance structures, including CEO-Chair separation, and the performance of Nigerian deposit money banks. The study utilized a sample of 10 deposit money banks from 2006 to 2011 and employed multiple regression analysis to determine the impact of governance structures on bank performance. The findings showed that banks with separate CEO and Chairman roles had better financial performance, reflected in higher deposit growth and profitability. The study concluded that separating the roles promotes transparency and accountability, which are crucial in improving public trust and encouraging deposit mobilization. Strong governance mechanisms, including CEO-Chair separation, were found to be a significant predictor of deposit base expansion in Nigerian banks.

Nwaeze (2020) investigated the role of corporate governance, particularly CEO-Chair separation, in deposit mobilization among commercial banks in Nigeria. The study adopted a cross-sectional research design, collecting data from 15 commercial banks operating in Nigeria between 2015 and 2019. Using panel regression analysis, the study found that banks with a separation of CEO and Chair roles experienced a significant increase in customer deposits. The results indicated that the separation of leadership roles led to more effective corporate oversight, enhancing depositor confidence and increasing the bank's capacity to attract more deposits. The study recommended that commercial banks in Nigeria adopt this governance practice to improve their financial base and promote sustainable growth.

Adebayo and Akinlo (2021) analyzed the impact of corporate governance mechanisms, including CEO-Chair separation, on deposit mobilization in Nigerian commercial banks. The research employed a time-series design, using data from 12 commercial banks over a 10-year period (2010-2020). The study used econometric models such as ordinary least squares (OLS) regression to assess the relationship between governance practices and deposit mobilization. The findings revealed that banks with separate CEO and Chair positions demonstrated higher rates of deposit growth. The study

concluded that CEO-Chair separation positively influences depositor trust by reducing the risk of managerial dominance, thus improving the bank's capacity to mobilize deposits. The research suggested that regulatory bodies should enforce the separation of these roles to strengthen governance in the Nigerian banking sector.

METHOD

This research adopted ex-post facto research design. Ex-post facto involves a systematic empirical inquiry, in which an observer has no direct control of independent variables because their manifestations have already occurred or because they are inherently not manipulated. The study basically employed secondary data sources. The data was extracted from audited financial statements of listed banks obtained from Nigerian Exchange Group websites, Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation Bulletin from 2006 to 2022. The population of the study comprises all the twenty-nine Commercial banks listed in Nigeria Exchange Group official website as at December 2023.

The economic model used in the study which was in line with what is mostly found in the literature is given as:

$$Y (\text{DMR, PLR}) = f(\text{CCS}) \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$\text{DMR} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{CCS}_{it} + \epsilon \dots (2)$$

$$\text{PLR} = \beta_0 + \beta_2\text{CCS}_{it} + \epsilon \dots (3)$$

Variables Definition and Measurement

CCS= CEO-Chairman Separation: It is measured as the ratio of delineated roles between Executive Directors and Chairman to the total roles at the end of the year expressed as percentage (SEC Code 2011, Tshipa 2017).

PLR= Performing Loan Ratio: it is measured as the performing loans divided by total loans and advances within the year expressed as percentage (Okpe 2016, John & Ibenta, 2016).

DMR= Deposit Mobilization Ratio: it measured as total deposit divided by total asset within the year expressed as percentage.

$\beta_1 - \beta_2$ are the coefficient of the parameter estimate.

β_0 the intercept

ϵ = error term

Both descriptive and regression analysis was utilized in the study. Descriptive statistics was computed using SPSS version 26 which amongst other things help show the pattern, distribution, deviation and nature of the data.

For the regression analysis, Panel Ordinary Least Square (OLS) Regression was used to test the hypotheses. The decision is that the null hypothesis will be rejected if the p-value < 0.05; otherwise, it will be accepted.

RESULTS

Descriptive Statistics

Analysis of descriptive statistics is carried out in this section so as to unveil the nature of data being used for analysis.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Focused Variable

	N Statistic	Minimum Statistic	Maximum Statistic	Mean Statistic	Std. Deviation Statistic	Skewness		Kurtosis	
						Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
DEPOSIT MOBILIZATION RATIO	170	9.56	97.43	29.8072	25.72894	1.435	.186	.540	.370
PERFORMING LOAN RATIO	170	14.00	93.10	71.8788	13.49352	-1.040	.186	1.072	.370
CEO-CHAIRMAN DUALITY	170	14.80	55.00	27.6412	9.94755	.221	.186	-1.199	.370
Valid N (listwise)	170								

Source; SPSS OUTPUT (2024)

From table 1 above the mean value of DMR is 29.8072, while the minimum and maximum values are 9.56 and 97.43 respectively. PLR is 71.87, while the minimum and maximum values are 14 and 93.43

respectively. This is indicating that the performing loans and deposit mobilization ratios for Commercial banks is relatively high within the period under review. The table shows that on average, during the period of the study, CCS is 27.64%. The results show that all the variables have mean values greater than their respective standard deviation.

Testing Hypotheses

Table 2: Model Summary for Hypotheses 1

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				Durbin-Watson	
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2		Sig. F Change
1	.337 ^a	.114	.106	.32214	.114	.641	6	30	.697	1.147

a. Predictors: (Constant), LgCCS,

b. Dependent Variable: LgDMR

Source: SPSS OUPUT (2024)

The result shown in Table 2 revealed that the R² statistic is 0.114 while the adjusted R² statistic is 0.106, and R statistic is 0.337. This shows that 11.4% of systematic variation explained the effect of Chairman-CEO Separation (CCS), on Deposit Mobilization Ratio (DMR).

Table 3: ANOVA Summary for Hypotheses 1

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.399	6	1.1066	10.641	.001 ^b
	Residual	3.113	163	.104		
	Total	3.512	169			

a. Dependent Variable: LgDMR

b. Predictors: (Constant), LgCCS,

The result in table 3 revealed that a regression significant P-value of 0.001 < F (10.641) which implies that the overall model is statistically significant at 0.05 alpha level Chairman-CEO Separation (CCS), on Deposit Mobilization Ratio (DMR) of Commercial Banks in Nigeria.

Table 4: Coefficients summary for Hypotheses 1

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.529	17.425		2.088	.000
	LgCCS	.150	.345	.082	2.434	.002

Source: SPSS OUT PUT (2024)

H0₁: CEO-chairman separation has no significant effect on the deposit mobilization ratio of Commercial banks in Nigeria.

The result in table 3 above shows that the coefficient β_2 , is .082, which implies that a unit increase in LgCCS by 1% would cause .082 increase in DMR when all other factors are kept constant. Also, the table revealed that LgCCS had a p-value of .002, which is less than the critical value of 0.05 (p<0.05). Hence, the null hypothesis (H0₂) is rejected. Therefore, CEO-chairman separation has a significant effect on the deposit mobilization ratio of Commercial banks in Nigeria.

H0₂: CEO-Chairman separation has no significant effect on performing loan ratio of Commercial banks in Nigeria.

The result in table 4 above shows that the coefficient β_8 , is .082, which implies that a unit increase in CCS by 1% would cause .130 increase in PLR when all other factors are kept constant. Also, the table revealed that CCS had a p-value of .000, which is less than the critical value of 0.05 (p<0.05). Hence, the null hypothesis (H0₈) is rejected. Therefore, CEO-chairman separation has a significant effect on the performing loan ratio of Commercial banks in Nigeria.

DISCUSSION

Effect of the CEO-Chairman separation on deposit mobilization ratio of Commercial banks in Nigeria.

Findings from hypothesis two revealed that CEO-Chairman separation has a weak positive relationship with deposit mobilization ratio of Commercial banks in Nigeria. Also, the findings revealed that CEO-Chairman separation has a significant effect on deposit mobilization ratio of Commercial banks in Nigeria. This implies that an increase in CEO-Chairman separation index will increase the deposit mobilization ratio of quoted Commercial banks in Nigeria. This may be attributed to This finding is supported Asogwa (2019), Gafoor *et al.* (2018). However, it is not in line with the findings of Abdulazeez *et al.* (2019) and Saha and Ghosh (2019).

Effect of the CEO-Chairman separation on performing loan ratio of Commercial banks in Nigeria.

Findings from hypothesis eight revealed that CEO-Chairman separation has a weak positive relationship with performing loan ratio of Commercial banks in Nigeria. Also, the findings revealed that CEO-Chairman separation has a significant effect on performing loan ratio of Commercial banks in Nigeria. This implies that as Commercial banks polarize their board leadership models, they would report consistent assets that would be reliable for an investment decision. This has significant implication for managerial policy. CEO-Chairman separation enhances firms' assets quality. These finding is consistent with previous findings that revealed that CEOs-Chairman separation promotes board independence, which ensures high-quality earnings (Asogwa 2019). The findings also authenticate Egbunike and Odum (2018)'s work that shows that top management leadership structures enhance earnings quality among the manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

CONCLUSIONS

The findings on the effects of CEO-Chairman separation on deposit mobilization and performing loan ratios in Nigerian commercial banks highlight the nuanced impact of corporate governance on bank performance. The results show that while the separation of the CEO and Chairperson roles has a weak but positive relationship with both deposit mobilization and performing loan ratios, the overall influence is significant. This suggests that separating these roles can enhance depositor confidence and improve asset quality, contributing to better financial performance. In light of these findings, Nigerian commercial banks and regulatory authorities should continue to prioritize corporate governance reforms that promote leadership separation and board independence. This would not only strengthen the financial stability of banks but also foster depositor trust and enhance overall economic development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In line with the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Regulators should enforce the CEO-Chairman separation policy more rigorously, as it has a significant positive impact on deposit mobilization in Nigerian commercial banks.
2. Bank boards should prioritize the adoption of CEO-Chairman separation to enhance governance and improve the performing loan ratio, ensuring better asset quality and financial stability.

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